

Managing Editor's Column

Vol. 4, No. 12; December 28, 1998

Dear Readers:

This is the 48. regular issue of J.UCS, i.e. we have now four full years of J.UCS behind us. With some 4000 pages this must be almost a record for an electronic journal. Please do keep supporting it by making sure that good papers are submitted, that we have enough help with reviewing and that we have enough readers.

Incidentally, if you want to (or know someone who might want to) join the Editorial Board you are welcome: we intend to extend the Editorial Board to be really sure that we have enough referees for all areas of Computer Science. The condition for becoming a member is to have at least a Ph.D. from a recognized institution and a solid publication record. Anyone interested, please contact me!

Starting with 1999, J.UCS will come with a different layout and will emphasize the possibility to add notes, both for yourself and the general public. We hope that this fairly unique feature will be used more in the future than it has been used in the past!

All that remains for me to do now is to hope that you have a good festive season behind you, to wish you good reading, thank you for your help in 1998 and wish you all the best for 1999!

Yours cordially,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer
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